

PHILOSOPHICAL FOUNDATIONS, ESSENCE, AND CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CONCEPT OF ECOCULTURE

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Abstract: In this article, it is known that in the third millennium, science and technology are developing at a rapid pace, causing great damage to the environment due to the disruption of the natural balance between man and nature. The importance of treating Mother Nature with perspective and leaving it beautiful and natural to the next generation was noted. There are people who believe that the more cruel a person is to nature, the more nature will respond to him in the same way. Environmental literacy (competency) is the level of natural-scientific knowledge that is the basis of human activity in relation to nature, special skills and abilities, as well as moral qualities.

Key words: tradition, belief, ecological thinking, ecological outlook, social existence, social consciousness, science and technology, ecological culture, ecological policy, Nature, society, human, ecological knowledge.

INTRODUCTION

Today, one of the urgent tasks is to form ecological culture among the members of the society. The concept of ecological culture is also comprehensive and includes most of human activities. The ecological way of thinking of a person depends on the natural-geographical climate and conditions of the region where he lives, the mentality of the nation or people he belongs to, the way of life, history, customs, beliefs, and the nature of the people living in a particular society. is inextricably linked with his worldview and his relations with him. Due to the interdependence and influence of these relations, an ecological worldview is formed in a person. In other words, the ecological worldview is manifested in the interrelationship of social existence and social consciousness. After all, it should be noted that "as a result of global climate changes on our planet and environmental problems in our region, new and unprecedented challenges and challenges appear in agriculture every year." For this, it is necessary to form moral-ecological consciousness in society and "to acquire modern knowledge, to be the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need." From this point of view, socio-philosophical research of ecological culture is one of the urgent tasks.

According to the concept of eliminating the ecological danger before the human society and moving to a sustainable path of development in the human society, which has been constantly changing for several thousand years, the main indicators of the scientific direction of geoecology are calculated, the use of nature and the product there is a need to monitor changes in indicators such as the amount of production, the number of people, the scale of natural resource use, the amount of anthropogenic pressure on nature, the balance of the

ecological and ethno-ecological landscape in space and time. This, in turn, shows the need for a historical approach along with innovative views to preserve the ecological balance.

It is known that in the third millennium, science and technology is developing at a rapid pace, causing great damage to the environment due to the disruption of the natural balance between man and nature. It is an important task of today to treat mother nature with perspective, to leave it beautiful and natural for future generations. As much as man treats nature with cruelty, nature also responds in the same way to man. To the extent that ecological culture is formed in the mind of each person, the society will also develop to that extent.

From the second half of the 20th century, a system of skeptic-pessimistic, even alarmist, fatalistic views was formed in the United States and developed Farb countries in relation to human activities in solving environmental problems. Although there are conflicting opinions about these views, each of them claims to be true in its own way, they have practical significance as they alert humanity to the threat of global problems. For example, the German philosopher E. Hanke said: "For the first time in history, man has acquired the power to destroy all mankind. In the dramatic situation that has arisen today, there are two alternatives: either destruction or salvation, it's up to us to realize it. Members of the "Club of Rome" J. Forrester, D. Meadows, Ya. Tinbergan, A. King and American scientist R. Falk (1886-1958) and Italian philosopher E. Severino (1929-2018) also express this opinion. In general, according to the conclusion of economist-environmental experts, most countries allocate 3-5% of GDP to natural environment protection. By increasing its amount by 5-7%, it is possible to achieve stability of the ecological situation. An increase of 7-10% will lead to a relatively healthy environmental situation. We can know from these statistical data that the ecological situation is deteriorating today. Therefore, the research of ecological culture within the framework of philosophical sciences and the development of ecological education among members of society remain important tasks.

Although the alternative views of the world scientific community about the role of the principle of global ecological tolerance in the issue of finding solutions to global problems have a utopian-ideal character far from practical life and scientific perfection, they use a relatively universal scientific theory and methodology in solving the universally pressing problems facing mankind in the future. should be recognized as a retrospective basis of development.

In recent years, special attention has been paid to the analysis of concepts such as "ecological attitude", "ecological consciousness", "ecological culture", "ecological policy" as a social phenomenon. The importance of these scientific studies is important in solving general philosophical, epistemological, methodological and praxeological issues. The commonality in the content of these concepts is to show that it is possible to strengthen the position of a person's social and political life, increase his activity and responsibility, only by analyzing the ecological activities in concrete directions. Also, the fundamental research of social, economic processes, cultural-educational factors and components affecting the formation and enrichment of a person's ecological culture in their interrelationship and integrity is of great importance. At this point, before studying the philosophical-methodological foundations, essence, and characteristics of the analysis of the concept of ecological culture, it is necessary to classify and analyze the categories of ecological consciousness, ecological worldview, and ecological activity, which are components of ecological culture. Based on the essence of the

matter, it is known that both the ecological culture of a person or society and their ecological outlook are formed in the interrelationship of social existence and systems of social consciousness. In this matter, M.S. Kogan: Culture is a systematic form of social existence, without understanding the essence of this system, the structural analysis of culture is incomplete. Only by adding the concept of culture to such concepts as "nature, society, man" will the analysis be completed. "Nature-society-man-culture" is a unique system, and it is a criterion for distinguishing the functions of their main components," he wrote.

Ecological knowledge is the information acquired by people about the protection of the natural environment, the rational use of natural resources, and the restoration of damaged natural complexes, that is, the degree to which this reality is reflected in human thinking.

Ecological culture is knowledge about nature, consciousness, perception, literacy, intellectual potential and the activity of knowing how to apply it in practice, a high indicator of activity in relation to the environment, a conscious and responsible approach. It contains a rational and responsible relationship between nature and man. According to the researcher Z. Yazdonov, ecological culture coordinates the mutual relations of the parts of the "nature-society-man" system, means the dialectical dependence of all beings in existence to humanity, encourages the preservation of environmental purity, and thereby serves to preserve the entire universe from degradation. is a philosophical-ethical category.

Ecological culture is rapidly developing as a system of certain types of views about the forms and principles of interaction between nature and society, human and nature, relations between society and the biosphere, and laws of harmony. Ecological culture is a product of ecological education and upbringing aimed at one goal, which indicates the necessary level of ecological education of a person. It includes the following elements: motives of ecological activity are scientific ecological knowledge, scientific ecological thinking is social ecological activity, ecological self-evaluation and self-control.

Ecological culture is the student's ability to organize nature and environmental protection in accordance with social requirements. Ecological activity is the process of ensuring nature and environment protection based on ecological knowledge. In higher educational institutions, in the family and in society, the discussion on environmental topics, roundtable discussions, excursions, debates, creative contests, meetings, socially useful work (Shabbalik, hashar, greening) etc. increase the effectiveness of environmental education. Personal examples of subjects participating in the educational process, educational resources, fiction, ideas of media materials (including the Internet) are considered important means of forming environmental culture in students.

In such a new type of society, priority is given not to change internal social relations, but to change the relationship between man and the natural environment. This requires a fundamental change in people's worldview: goodness, positivity, progressiveness, and the like. From this point of view, "ecological culture, like any other social system, develops on the basis of the laws of dialectics, in which there are new, progressive and old, regressive phenomena, and there is a constant struggle between them. Therefore, ecology is an object of regular exchange of new and old, positive and negative, beneficial and harmful phenomena and realities.

In this sense, the relationship, differences and differences between ecological culture and the ecological outlook of a person, in our opinion, can be seen in the following:

- ecological culture has relative stability in relation to the ecological worldview, and the practical mutuality of ideas, values, customs and traditions and tendency to integration is its essence;

- ecological worldview has the character of dynamic change compared to ecological culture due to the fact that it is formed in the way of the practical activity, knowledge, experience, attitude of a certain person and grows in harmony with the phenomena of natural and social processes;

- to correctly understand the influence of the relationship between nature and society on the content of ecological culture, to rationally implement it, to acquire ecological knowledge and skills, to produce within the scope of one's profession and potential serves for environmentalization. Researcher V. O. Levinskaya substantiates the above-mentioned opinion as follows: "Ecological culture is a rational creative approach to mastering natural resources, and in this process a responsible approach to the development, distribution and use of ecological values emerges." In general, in spite of mutual relations, differences and differences in ecological culture and personal ecological worldview, the mentality of people and the socio-ecological needs of society have a decisive importance in the formation of these two concepts.

Ecological culture covers the following: culture of nature protection, culture of use of natural resources, culture of changing the ecological system. A person who has formed an ecological culture in himself deeply understands that care for nature protection at the scale of a district has an effective effect on the ecological situation far away. Elimination of deficiencies in the natural environment is the work of all nations and peoples. Unifying their activities towards one goal is an important condition for solving the environmental problem.

Ecological culture relies not only on universal human values, but also universal values, that is, values common to man and nature. This culture promotes harmony and harmony between man and nature. Ecological culture has its own natural scientific basis, it is included in the concept of modern scientific synergetics, which determines the systematic and integrated perception of the world. Ecological culture is the main and sufficient part of the development of universal culture, and it characterizes a deep understanding of the importance and urgency of solving environmental problems in human life and development. Ecological culture is conceived as a part of the general culture, it is a separate type of social culture and has its own essence and function. Ecological culture is defined as an open system of values, the purpose of which is to preserve nature, as an indicator of individual values. Tariffs for ecological culture are different. For example, ecological culture is a creative activity in mastering nature, in the process of which ecological values are fulfilled, distributed and used. The development of environmental culture is one of the urgent problems in the current period. Ecological culture is a special qualitative level of social, material, practical, spiritual-theoretical relations to nature, it directly includes and describes the process of re-appropriation of life. Material and cultural aspects of ecological culture should be developed proportionately. Education based on the interests of creating an ecological culture is becoming the main direction embodying education in other fields. Ecological education is the basis for the formation of ecological culture. The universal importance of environmental problems and the determination of the fate and value of humanity requires the unification of various educational and educational fields based on common interests. This requires the development of universal methodology. The development of ecological ideology, a wider

ecological culture, envisages the need for a synthesis of rational attitudes to nature, which exist in different types of cultures, both in the East and in the West.

"Ethical-ecological awareness", "Ecological responsibility", "Ecological willfulness", "Respect for ecological values" should be defined as the basic qualities of ecological knowledge and ecological culture. The formation of ecological culture is based on the theory of scientific social development, which includes the laws of social ecology, a new science that is currently being formed. If the traditional sciences focused on the study of natural processes arose based on the needs of society to expand its influence on nature in order to "subdue" nature, then social ecology is the way of society to protect and improve the natural conditions of people's lives. arose due to the need to harmonize interaction with nature.

Despite the fact that the concept of ecological culture is a relatively new concept, there are many views and definitions about it in the current philosophical literature. In particular, N.Sh. Bozorova interprets that "Ecological culture is the protection of nature, the rational use of natural resources, the formation of ecological feelings, an active outlook on life, and the acquisition of ecological knowledge." U.G. Saidova defines this concept as "ecological culture is knowledge about nature, consciousness, perception, literacy, intellectual potential and the ability to apply it in practice, a high indicator of human activity in relation to the environment, a conscious and responsible approach", - comments.

The works of researchers E.J.Ikromov, A.A.Khotamov are focused on the issues of forming an individual's ecological culture. They tried to clarify these problems by researching the conceptual approach that "personal ecological culture is the product of all educational work". At the same time, the functions of ecological culture in enriching the ecological outlook of the individual are also justified through a series of analyzes and conclusions.

Ecological thinking determines the level of a person's knowledge, culture, education. Every person with a high ecological culture is committed to the goal of organizing and creating the best conditions of the mental, emotional and social environment for the further development of a person in his professional and non-professional activities, as well as for the protection and strengthening of his health. iy lives by practice. Forming a new ecological way of thinking is an extremely difficult task. A few years ago, under the slogans of "subjugation of nature" and "victory over nature", people attacked nature with their selfish actions. It was never thought that no one could ever win over nature. Now we need such education and upbringing that all our future generations will fully master the philosophy of ecological ethics.

The elements of ecological culture are considered: ecological knowledge, skills and abilities, beliefs and views, the need to rely on national values, first of all, at the local level, in enriching the ecological consciousness and worldview of each person, which governs his activities in the natural environment, and the priority of their features related to universal value. worth noting. Because ecological culture means a practical attitude to the environment and nature, people's activities and behavior in the field of ecology, consciousness formed at a certain level and direction.

The concept of "ecological culture" is defined by I.T. Suravegina as follows: "Ecological culture" is a growing unity of a person's ecological knowledge and his positive attitude to this knowledge. In our opinion, in this definition, more attention is paid to the spiritual components of the individual and society, and not enough attention is paid to the ecological practice. According to A.A. Melkumova and G.I. Lyubkarsky, ecological culture consists of several components: beliefs, knowledge, skills and competences, norms of activity and

behavior, and emotions. That is, it is concluded that the main foundations of the concept of "ecological culture" are ecological knowledge, ecological awareness, practical skills and qualifications for nature protection.

Ethical-ecological consciousness is an important eco-cultural quality of a person, and it is the process of his emotional knowledge of the environment: he feels, perceives, imagines the objects and events in the environment, can compare the objects and events of the environment, on the basis of intelligence and depth implies the need to have practical skills in nature protection.

Environmental responsibility is manifested in the education of "attitude" and "responsibility" in a person. Such an attitude is formed only as a result of realizing the consequences of a person's unknowingly and thoughtlessly negative impact on nature and the desire to eliminate such an impact. Environmental responsibility includes qualities such as love for mother nature, personal responsibility, conscientiousness, devotion to duty, and caution.

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